

A Practical Guide to Implementing a Federated Information Governance Framework: Supporting Summary and Facilitator Guidance Notes

To begin the SATRE-based federation process, key terminologies (with narrow scope, not umbrella terms) should be gathered, and all partners should decide their definitions. A joint session should then be held to agree consensus definitions. The individual partners should then escalate the consensus definitions for confirmation within their own organisations for use within the federation going forwards.

Next, all partners must agree the scope of federation- this is a critical step, as setting the boundaries for the types of research permitted lays the groundwork for an overarching IG framework, as opposed to generating agreements on a per-project basis..

For the equivalence exercise, individual full SATRE self-assessments should be undertaken by each partner organisation, then brought together into a single document; a colour-coded heatmap provides a useful visual representation for subsequent workshops and discussions. Prior to running the full exercise, federations may benefit from a pre-meeting where 3-5 example SATRE criteria are discussed, to practice and troubleshoot the planned process.

The equivalence exercise itself is best run as a facilitated workshop with the appropriate subject-matter experts for each SATRE pillar. For each criterion, encourage the group to consider whether it is critical for federation. Where it is, explore where partners' practices are equivalent, and whether it is 'non-negotiable' that processes be equivalent or there is acceptable variability- the limits of which must be defined. The environment of these workshops must be safe and structured, so differences can be openly discussed.

To maintain equivalence over time, it is recommended that the federation appoints a designated IG team, with formalised scope and roles and responsibilities, to carry out an annual review. Additional reviews must be completed if there are relevant legislative or regulatory changes occurring outside the annual review cycle.

Facilitators should encourage each partner organisation to gather feedback from their data providers, and any concerns regarding the federation model. They should then support the group to identify local policies which need amending or creating, and conduct an options analysis to weigh the feasibility, risks, and benefits of producing a single, unified set of statements for federation with which to amend all policies, versus independently written amendments by each partner.

The full report for the PANORAMA Work Package 1 Report ('An Evaluation of the Effectiveness of the SATRE Specification to Support the Creation of a Federated Information Governance Framework') is accessible via Zenodo.

Included here is a simplified reference guide to support the facilitated workshop.

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Define a Shared Language

Define Scope of Federated Analytics

Participating organisations must explicitly define the scope of federation, and identify which projects cannot be considered under the over-arching IG framework.

Establish Equivalence

Monitoring Change Over Time

Gain Support From Data Providers

Design the Federated Information Governance Framework

Determine the Appetite for a Unified Information Governance Statement for Amendments

Conduct an Options Analysis of the feasibility, risks and benefits of 2 approaches:

- Decentralised: Each SDE amends its policies independently.
- Collaborative: A unified IG statement with agreed language is developed and incorporated across all SDEs.

Organisations write a unified statement using agreed shared language, for each SDE to apply to amend their local IG agreements

Each organisation amends their local IG agreements using local language